

Lay health workers in primary and community health care for chronic conditions: diabetes treatment

Cochrane review update

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Excluded studies (with reason for exclusion)

Ref ID	Bibliography	Reason for exclusion
1	2004. Home-based programme significantly reduces depressive symptoms and improves health status in chronically ill older adults with minor depression or dysthymia Evidence-based healthcare and public health, 8(5): 257-258.	Study design not relevant
58	2018. One-Year Adherence to the Otago Exercise Program With or Without Motivational Interviewing in Community-Dwelling Older Adults Journal of aging and physical activity, 26(3): 390-395.	Study design not relevant
87	2018. Results from the core trial in Southern Province, Zambia, comparing two reactive responses in a quest to accelerate elimination of malaria American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene, 99(4): 205-206.	Intervention/ comparison not relevant
89	2018. Assessing group antenatal care model fidelity in 18 rwandan health centers: the first 6 months International journal of gynaecology and obstetrics, Conference: 22nd FIGO World Congress of Gynecology and Obstetrics. Brazil. 143(Supplement 3): 642-643.	Intervention/ comparison not relevant
94	2018. Universal versus conditional day 3 follow-up for children with non-severe unclassified fever at the community level in the Democratic Republic of the Congo: a cluster-randomized, community-based non-inferiority trial Plos medicine, 15(4): #Pages#.	Intervention/ comparison not relevant
95	2018. Comparison of the effect of control, presence of a skilled birth attendant and reflexotherapy on labour outcomes in terms of pain, duration of labour and birth satisfaction among primigravid women-a pilot study Biomedical research (india), 29(17): 3292-3302.	Type of healthcare professional not relevant
96	2018. Comparison of the effectiveness of reflexotherapy with skilled birth attendant on labor outcomes in terms of psychophysiological variables among primigravid women - a pilot study National journal of physiology, pharmacy and pharmacology, 8(8): 1179-1187.	Setting not relevant
124	2019. Lay field-worker–led school health program for primary schools in low- and middle-income countries Pediatrics, 143(4): #Pages#.	Study design not relevant
129	2019. Use of mobile immunization teams to increase influenza vaccination coverage among healthcare workers. A community intervention trial Revista espanola de salud publica, 93(#issue#): #Pages#.	Type of healthcare professional not relevant
137	Abdulahi, M., Fretheim, A., Magnus, J. H. 2018. Effect of breastfeeding education and support intervention (BFESI) versus routine care on timely initiation and exclusive breastfeeding in Southwest Ethiopia: study protocol for a cluster randomized controlled trial BMC pediatrics, 18(1): 313.	Intervention/ comparison not relevant
144	Adams-Campbell, L. L. 2017. Metabolic syndrome and breast cancer risk among black women: an exercise intervention Cancer research, 77(22): #Pages#.	Type of healthcare professional not relevant
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7253	Hygiene, London School of, Medicine, Tropical, Protection, Health, Organisation, Research, TPO, HealthNet, International, Medical Emergency Relief 2012. Cluster Randomised Trial of Malaria RDTs Used by CHWs in Afghanistan #journal#, #volume#(#issue#): #Pages#.	Intervention/ comparison not relevant

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7354	Rochester, University of, Health, Eunice Kennedy Shriver National Institute of Child, Development, Human 2019. Promotion of Successful Parenting #journal#, #volume#(#issue#): #Pages#.	Intervention/ comparison not relevant
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